

NERVOUSNESS BEHAVIOR OF FOREIGNERS TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING IN CHINA: THE MAJOR CONCERNS TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING

Zulfiqar Ali¹, Nasir Aman², Hasin Bano^{*3}, Ujala Liaqat⁴,

¹Department of Management Sciences and Engineering, School of Management and Economics, Kunming University of Science and Technology, Yunnan 650500, China.

²University of Science and Technology of China.

³Lecturer Department of Computer Science, University of Baltistan Skardu, Pakistan, PhD Scholar Kunming University of Science and Technology, Yunnan, China.

⁴National Defense University Islamabad.

¹zulfi.hunzai86@gmail.com, ²nasiraman@mail.ustc.edu.cn, ³hasin.bano@uobs.edu.pk, ⁴ujalaliaqat5@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15308009>

Keywords

Online Shopping Behavior, China, Stimulus Organism Response Model.

Article History

Received on 15 March 2025

Accepted on 15 April 2025

Published on 30 April 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Hasin Bano

Abstract

This study's major purpose was to identify the underlying causes of concern felt by international individuals in China when engaged in online purchasing. To accomplish this, an S-O-R (Stimulus-Organism-Response) based theoretical model was employed, taking into account various factors such as acculturation and language barriers as stimuli for evaluating their influence on the organism—specifically, E-customer satisfaction—and then examining the response regarding online purchase intention as a means of gauging the foreigners' discomfort. Using an online questionnaire, data were collected and analyzed using structural equation modeling. Using confirmatory factor analysis approaches, construct validity and underlying structural linkages were determined. The results demonstrate a positive and statistically significant link between stimulators including language obstacles, acculturation, and online privacy risk, disturbed information searching, and online purchasing intent. Yet, there was no correlation between bad foreigner orientation or subpar website navigation flow and intents to make digital transactions. This analysis has significant significance for its capacity to shed light on the various aspects foreign citizens assess when selecting whether or not to engage in digital transactions in China. The practical applicability of this study's findings for foreigners residing in China, as well as for large e-commerce platforms and other businesses operating within the country's borders, makes them very valuable. In addition, major theoretical contributions and pertinent policy implications resulting from these findings have been made.

INTRODUCTION

The online shoppers' ratio has increased in China in approximately ten years from about 160.51 to 710.27 million (Hao & Choi, 2019). The percentage of

online commerce accounts in China is about 42% worldwide, and it manages more transactions than Japan, Germany, the UK, and other countries per

year. T-Mall is a shopping source owned by Alibaba, whose market share is approximately 60% and has about 500 million active customers. This mall sells high-quality and authentic products, consisting of different products such as home appliances, cars, electronics, etc. It has gained the attention of many customers and the trust of many users to increase its productivity (Singh & Srivastava, 2018). The majority of foreign under study status prefer to do their grocery shopping, buy clothes, and other shopping for themselves online. Furthermore, they exclusively buy their necessities for daily life online. As e-commerce develops and e-platforms evolve, Chinese consumers have access to cutting-edge marketplaces and novel ways to conduct business online. Foreigners shop primarily on Taobao (97%), Jingdong (JD) (79%) and Pingduoduo (59%) reported by the work of (Islam, 2021). Connecting the online shopping platforms, they apt consumption options along with e-commerce barriers in developing nations and low internet penetration in China up to 52.2% (Jain & Kulhar, 2019; Alyoubi, 2015).

High traffic is mapped during the holidays and festivals in relation to online purchasing in China, which is slowed by time, acculturative environment, and consumer activities (Guan et al., 2020). Studies have been undertaken to investigate hypotheses regarding correlations between variables such as customers' perceptions of risk, the persuasiveness of websites, and consumers' tendency to shop online (Clemes, et al., 2014). On the basis of social cognitive theory, a study model of online shopping behavior is proposed, which implies that a trusting environment has a positive influence on online shopping behavior and that perceived website complexity has a negative and direct influence on online purchasing behavior (Cheng & Fu, 2018).

Few researchers and analysts have studied the effect of online privacy risk (Pratama et al., 2017) and poor foreigner orientation (PFO) on the customer's overall intent to purchase online (Taghipour et al., 2018). So, analysts wish to observe the effect of the endeavor. In the present study, the Chinese foreigners' nervousness while making online purchases is proxied through their online purchase intention. Other researchers and practitioners are interested in the problems foreigners face in terms of

their shopping experience, both online and in-person (Zhang, et al., 2018). The number of foreigners in China has increased as educational, and work opportunities have opened (Islam, 2021). The observance of these predicaments that people face while living there will only make the country more habitable.

Additionally, commerce in China has been on the rise, and a better understanding of the challenges experienced by foreigners is essential to making improvements. Previous research indicated that international visitors to China used credit cards to make purchases online. Due to the disorganized presentation of closely related products on e-commerce sites, this approach has largely superseded the conventional one (Rashed & Ashraf Un, 2016; Cheng, & Fu, (2018).

One previous study showed that privacy risk leads to leakages of personal information on google's sites to receiving unconditional messages from scam websites to purchase specific products (Mittal, 2013). Some data in the previous literature showed that Chinese online products contained only a little information about their specification, which decreases the chances of purchasing by foreigners (Valaei et al., 2016). The main problem is that there is a restriction in China on to use of social media. Moreover, there is the problem of different cultures, language barriers, pollution, etc. A language barrier makes it difficult for foreigners to become friends with the Chinese.

In accordance with the aforementioned concerns, the subsequent research objectives have been established:

- To assess the influence of factors such as acculturation, linguistic obstacles, and online privacy risks on the online purchasing intentions of foreign individuals residing in China.
- To examine the consequences of inadequate website design and insufficient orientation for foreigners on their online purchase intention within a Chinese context.
- To scrutinize the effect that difficulty in information acquisition imparts upon online purchasing intent among foreign residents in China.
- To appraise the mediating role played by electronic customer satisfaction.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: the second section of the literature review focuses on the assessment of the past literature on the challenges of foreigners in China; the third chapter of the study methodology focuses on the methods, designs, and tools; the fourth section of the analysis and interpretation is used to analyze and interpret the results extracted from the data; and the fifth chapter focuses on discussing the findings.

Literature Overview

2.1. Conceptual Framework

This study employs the S-O-R model to identify the online and international consumers' intrinsic motives for online buying and how these motivations influence their level of online shopping satisfaction. Several studies have demonstrated that there is a favorable effect on the emotional condition of customers only if they are satisfied with their online purchases and buying experience (Jackson & Dear, 2016). This study emphasizes the uneasiness of foreigners in relation to their intention to shop online in China. Using the theory of Stimulus, Organism, and Reaction (OSR), the proxy of working variables is seated as an anxiety construct in the investigation of foreigners' online purchasing intent. According to studies, online shopping on well-known websites is accompanied by a high level of satisfaction and a low level of danger (Boban et al., 2021; Islam, 2021). In addition, it was determined that the relationship between web atmospherics and website satisfaction was totally mediated by components and variables of pleasure and pleasure. In addition, the outcomes of the study indicate that a website's cues have a direct impact on the behavior and attitude of customers, as well as their response attitudes. In addition, the study examined the impact of website signals on customers' primary website-directed behaviors as well as their related reactions and responses (Liao & Cheung; 2001). Moreover, the S-O-R model explains that the stimulus triggers a response based primarily on an organism's internal observation, which influences the customer's buy intention. According to Buxbaum (2016), this inner observation can be conscious and unconscious. According to a study conducted in China, Hong Kong, and Singapore, consumers place a high value on maintaining their privacy when buying online,

particularly when it comes to protecting their financial information (Wee & Ramachandra; 2000). The purchasing online is complex in China under time inconvenience, navigation, ordering, inappropriate websites (Chen et al., 2015; Bhatnagar & Ghosh, 2004). In a study that compared conventional shopping with online shopping, the results showed that online shopping was associated with a significantly higher incidence of customers falling victim to fraudulent financial practices (Nazir et al., 2012). But most of the online selling websites in China are losing trust due to poor management and output to buyers. The S-O-R model maintains the buyer's satisfaction by alerting vendors' online website malfunctioning, concerned with quality of products, and gives easy access to foreigners in online shopping from China (Lim et al., 2016).

2.2. The Relationship between Acculturation and Online Purchase Intention

An individual's cultural inclinations have a significant impact on their propensity to make a purchase on an e-commerce site, a phenomenon known as acculturation. (Jamal et al., 2019). The product development is efficiently based keeping the in view the global diversity as success key for the Chinese manufacturers. Products in an online store should be available in different languages because this will have a direct effect on the OPI and make the store more profitable (Dey et al., 2020). Moreover, cultural domain of the foreigners keeps them limited in provisos of buying habits. Online purchase intention is considered an essential market strategy that can be helpful in acculturation in the marketplace (Kizgin et al., 2020). The conceptual framework has proved that the intrinsic motivations of online customers directly influence the satisfaction level of online buying. The previous study showed that foreigners in China made online shopping receiving tags of Chinese cultures (Dai et al., 2009). The people of different countries have their own cultures and interests in products offered by various websites. Still, in China, they mix the cultures or only show Chinese cultural products which are not suitable for foreigners to purchase. Therefore, foreigners do not prefer Chinese online franchise products. Various studies are also conducted in this regard in different countries but

they have the different culture from China (Weitz, 2010). It is necessary for Chinese online selling websites to show the products of all cultures, so that everybody can buy the outcome of their own will according to their culture (Valaei et al., 2016). Thus, in line with the above discussion, this study proposes the following hypothesis;

H1: Acculturation has a huge effect on the Perception of customers.

2.3 Online Privacy Risk and Buying Intention

According to Ahmad, Attiq, Ahmad, Ilyas, and Kulsoom (2019), online privacy presumes the mandate and right of individual seclusion regarding the caching, provision, reusing of third parties, and showing of data to personal online. Invasion of privacy in the context of e-commerce is described by Kiely (1997) as the unwarranted acquisition, dissemination, or other use of personally identifiable information. Online shoppers in China are more likely to reveal sensitive financial information, such as their debit and credit card numbers, to third parties, according to a recent study (Wee & Ramachandra; 2000; Liao & Cheung, 2001). Online buying and data privacy in Chinese marketplaces is also studied by polling 412 people (Guo & Jaafar, 2011). Online shopping giants in China are engaged in stalking, which websites the public stays with and then incorporates the data, exemplar by dispatching goods that are promoted majorly based on one's web browsing data. Those distressed about online privacy generally plot several OPRs, occurrences that can deal with privacy which may be confronted mainly by online operations. Moreover, information and data mishandling is one of the essential OPRs which rightly affects the OPI of customers and further leads to foreigners' nervousness during online shopping in China (Bhatti & Rehman, 2020). Previous literature data showed that most foreigners only made online shopping from Chinese online shopping and its related websites (Kumar et al., 2014). The buyers are highly concerned with information privacy, identity theft and the products according to their intentions (Islam, 2021). The main issue which the foreigners faced most was the language. The Chinese online shoppers' websites showed the products in Chinese only, which is a big hurdle for online buyers, they order the product of their own intention but the

online shoppers provide the other product (Zhao, 2013). In this regard, we concluded that online shoppers should deliver the names of the products in an international language like English, with images of products, so that foreigners can easily buy the items of their will. The sellers or shoppers should provide privacy and fulfil all the intentions and needs of buyers and their privacy too (Goldstein, 2001).

Therefore, based on the above discussion, the given effort hypothesized that;

H2: Internet privacy risk has a substantial impact on the intention to purchase online.

2.4. The Relationship between Bad Website Navigation and Online Purchasing Intention

The vast majority of customers and end-users are looking for data online that will assist them in drawing useful and more innovative conclusions regarding their online shopping experiences. A study conducted in China with 312 participants reveals that low-quality websites are responsible for a low rate of customer retention among foreigners (Liao & Cheung; 2001). According to Chi (2018), 86% of online users will research product information before they make a purchase online and in the store, and this buying attitude trend emphasizes the significance of a website flow for today's businesses in China. The article investigates the link between perceived website complexity and online shopping behavior, highlighting the importance of the online store setting (Cheng & Fu, 2018). The previous literature showed that online shopping in China is more incredible, and foreigners mostly made shopping from Chinese websites. The main issues that foreigners mostly face are privacy risks, poor flow of the website and purchase intentions (Gill et al., 2006). Due to the poorly designed website, the customers had difficulty completing their payments online. On occasion, individuals pay money through an online transaction; nevertheless, as a result of problems with the websites of various retailers, they wind up losing their money without actually purchasing the things (Eroglu et al., 2003; Shirk, 2007).

In most cases, the products shown on the website and the received products have differences that do not fulfill the buyer's intentions. Therefore, online

shopping in China is at risk. Foreigners prefer other countries where they feel satisfied with their products and pay money through the online transaction (Yaobin et al., 2007). The significance of a website flow for marketing extends to almost every aspect of the digital marketing strategy because, according to Ajay Kaushik and Potti Srinivasa (2017), poor website flow affects the intention of online customers and consumers. Moreover, insignificant website flow makes it difficult for customers to search for the products and services they need, directly affecting customers' purchase intentions. In addition to this, a poorly designed website flow has the potential to lower the quality of the navigation system, the content, and the visual elements that are included on the website. Customers who shop online are more likely to recall the message and the product description if they are clear and succinct, and if the information relates to something the client can relate to (King et al., 2016). So, in line with the above discussion, the given study suggests the following hypothesis;

H3: Low website and app development and flow has a substantial impact on consumers' online purchasing intent.

2.5. The Link between Bad Foreigner Orientation and Intention to Make an Online Transaction

Foreign consumers in China have access to the most cutting-edge distribution channels and innovative possibilities for buying and selling through online podiums as a result of the rapid transformation of e-platforms and the rise of e-commerce in the country (Islam, 2021). A platform orientation lean business structure that primarily requires management and employees to focus on the shifting requirements and preferences of its international clients is described as having platform orientation. (Taghipour et al., 2018). A company strategic fit reflects consumer needs at the central point of purchase intention for the organizational machinery (Bashir et al., 2019). Online shopping adoption and hypothesized links such e-commerce decision variables, website linkage and consumer risk have been tested (Clemes et al., 2014). Most modern online companies and giants have neglected the system to a more foreigner-oriented approach to product design, development as well as marketing strategy, this directly influence the

process of OPI. Therefore, to fill this gap management of online businesses should introduce products and employees would be in charge of developing them majorly according to the plans and drawings. Thus, in the light of the above arguments the present study hypothesized that;

H4: Poor foreigner orientation has a major impact on online buying intention.

2.6. Correlation between Language Barrier and Inclination to Purchase Online

A sizable portion of internet shoppers either don't bother with international vendors or stick to those based in countries with which they feel they share a linguistic affinity (Islam, 2021). According to Zhu, Mou, and Benyoucef (2019), cultural and language barriers can majorly lead to poor communication, fear, and resulting poor degree of OPI. The inability to communicate is often cited as the primary cause for a lack of market interaction among non-native speakers of the language (Junqian Ma, 2020). According to Lisichkova and Othman (2017), up to 62% of businesses believe that language barriers hinder their business progress because foreigners feel hesitant and nervous about purchasing local products and services. On the other hand, 48% manifest that misunderstanding during their business deals with foreigners has majorly resulted in financial losses for them. The most significant financial losses for organizations doing business in China are, according to a new poll, the result of language problems. (Rashed & Ashraf Un, 2016). Language barriers can create issues with foreigners because foreigners won't be able to communicate with the service providers, their staff and suppliers, which directly affects the intentions of online customers. Consequently, the present study hypothesized that;

H5: Language limitations have a substantial impact on online buying intent.

2.7. The Connection between Problematic Information-Seeking and Online Purchasing Intent

Information seeking is the overall process or activity of attempting to obtain data and information about the product and service before purchasing online. The prior investigation showed that most foreigners preferred online shopping from China. Online

shopping is growing in different countries (Yaobin et al., 2007). Foreigners prefer online shopping from those countries 'websites, which provide better information on the website and the quality of products buyers receive. In this regard, we concluded that in this era, Chinese online vendors are not giving proper instructions, the products on the website and the products that buyers receive (Nuryakin & Farida, 2016). The website's instructions are mainly Chinese, a significant barrier for foreigners. Websites are not easy to access and do not show product details properly, which affects online shopping from China. It is necessary to enhance the website's trustworthy and proper product guide so that foreigners prefer shopping from Chinese online vendors (Shambaugh, 2015). According to Lissitsa and Kol (2019), information seeking is a type of thought process that majorly leads a customer to identify a need, develop options and then select a particular product and brand, and if this process becomes troubled for a customer due to language barrier than this directly affect the purchase intention of the customer in a positive way. Moreover, information-seeking is connected to a variety of interpersonal communication behaviors. If this process makes some trouble for information seekers, then this affects the customer's purchase intention. Therefore, the present research effort hypothesized that;

H6: For the Status of foreigners in China, worrisome information searching has a huge impact.

2.8. The Function of E-customer Satisfaction as a Mediator in the Relationship between Acculturation and OPI

It has been stated by Khatoon et al. (2020) that there is a significant impact of E-customer satisfaction on the direct nexus between OPI and acculturation. Customers can analyze and interpret the products online using social media and determine the quality of their products according to their culture (Vakulenko et al., 2019). Social media or e-commerce has made it easy for customers to buy products online as online shops have provided information regarding the product, such as its quality, size, color, etc. The conceptual framework has proved that there is a positive impact on consumers' emotional state only if they obtain online satisfaction

from their purchases. The reported work leads to the establishment of the following hypothesis;

H7: Significantly, e-customer satisfaction mediates the relationship between acculturation and OPI.

2.9. E-customer Satisfaction's Moderating Effect on the relationship between Online Privacy Risk and OPI

E-customer satisfaction or social media has provided customers with privacy so no one can check their account without their authentication, and no unauthorized person can use it (Khatoon et al., 2020). A low-risk rate in online purchasing directly impacts the OPI as the customer's attention can be gained quickly. Rahi et al. (2020) Have described that E-customer has been introduced in online shopping to focus on the trust and satisfaction of the customers. The conceptual framework has stated that E-customer can be defined with the help of different factors and variables concerned with pleasure. Consequently, based on the above discussion, the current study hypothesized that;

H8: The association between OPR and foreign OPI is moderately mediated by e-customer satisfaction.

2.10. The Mediating Influence of E-commerce Satisfaction on the Linkage between Poor Website Flow and OPI

Research conducted by Jeon and Jeong (2017) has briefly explained that if an online store's poor website flow will negatively affect the OPI, it is necessary to have a reliable and efficient website flow. E-customer satisfaction will only be provided if there is no poor website flow and the online purchase intention is efficient (Vohra & Bhardwaj, 2019). The main reason for the aversion to online purchasing is the lack of trust, so E-customer satisfaction and resolution of website issues are essential to satisfy the customers. The conceptual framework has stated that website cues highly affect customer behavior and attitudes, either positively or negatively. So, in light of the above findings, the current study suggests that;

H9: E-customer satisfaction considerably mediates the relationship between foreigners' PWF and OPI.

2.11. The Intermediating E-commerce Satisfaction in the Inter-Dependence between Poor Foreigner Orientation and OPI

The role of foreigner orientation is essential and significant for people's knowledge and purchase intention while doing e-commerce. It is evaluated that online shopping has experienced massive and explosive growth over the last few decades in China compared to traditional shopping. However, customer satisfaction is vital here, especially for foreigners. The foreigner's orientation regarding online shopping and information seeking is shallow, directly affecting the people's purchase intention(Kaya et al., 2019). Therefore, the e-commerce industry in China is continuously doing efforts to formulate different strategies and minimize the gap between foreigners and online shopping platforms. Thus, the whole discussion formed the following hypothesis,

H10: Satisfaction of e-customers has a substantial moderating effect on the connection between bad foreigner orientation and OPI.

E-customer satisfaction is a term frequently used in e-marketing. According to (Opoku, 2016), it is a process usually carried out to empower customers and consumers and to fulfill their future needs and demands. E-customer satisfaction also provides a mechanism mainly used to overcome some challenges and language barriers consumers face and is also a leading indicator of consumer purchase intentions and loyalty. According to (Cheng et al.,

2017), E-customer satisfaction is one of the essential steps and indicators of OPIs and degrees of loyalty. Thus, the above entire discussion leads to the establishment of the following hypothesis;

H11: E-customer satisfaction has a substantial moderating effect on the association between language barrier and organizational performance indicators (OPI).

2.12. The Role of E-customer Satisfaction as a Moderator in the Relationship between Disturbed Information Seeking and OPI

Growing online businesses in China are more likely to prioritize foreign customer success than those with stagnant or reduced revenue. According to Rita et al. (2019), successful customers can become an important asset and the company's best salespeople. Recent indicators showed that 75% of individuals had shared favorable experiences with online companies and giants in the past year. Moreover, keeping the current customers happy through providing adequate online facilities in almost all languages and product information with ease of searching may prove to be good business and enhance foreigners' intentions in the long term. Hence, in line of the above findings, the given research effort suggests the following hypothesis;

H12: Significantly mediating the relationship between problematic information seeking and OPI is e-consumer happiness.

Research Model

The study framework reflects the buying patterns of the foreigners living in the mainland China. This research work contributes highlighting the external factor that will affect conditions and emotions leads to human response. Furthermore, the empirical evidence came from the study findings open up ways of thinking, capturing and clearing, purchasing intention under technological edge (fig.1).

Research Method

3.1. Data and Sample Selection

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the causes of foreigners' apprehension over the scale of internet shopping in China. To achieve the aims of this study, the researcher employed a survey-based analytic strategy. For this goal, the researcher has designed an online survey method. According to previous academics, online structured surveys are an excellent tool for collecting data (Granello & Wheaton, 2004). The poll was constructed using the most recent research topics discovered through a literature review. Non-random sampling, also known as purposive sampling, which is not particular to an underlying theory or a predetermined number of participants. Under knowledge and experience, the knowledge virtue is participant readiness to generate information, as determined by the researcher (Bernard, 2002). Purposive rivets involve locating and selecting individuals or groups who are knowledgeable and skilled about a phenomenon of interest (Spradley, 1979; Cresswell & Clark, 2011). The purpose of purposive sampling is to focus on individuals with specific characteristics who will be able to contribute more to the research (Etikan et al., 2015).

The information was gathered during the first quarter of 2020. A statement of confidentiality that ensured the respondents' anonymity was also included to increase the social desirability and sample size. A total of 1200 people were included in the population. However, filter questions were used to ascertain that the sample represented foreigners and not nationals of the country and also the people who had generic information regarding online shopping. The following questions filtered the potential respondents: "Is china your home country?"—those individuals who are not Chinese excluded from this study. The second question that

was inferred from the respondents was, "Do you know about online shopping?". The respondents that responded negatively to the second question were also discarded. Thus, after filtering the responses, the final sample represented 550 total responses. Out of 443 have been used for the final analysis, the questionnaires with missing values and repeated answers were also discarded.

3.2. Common Method Bias

This research work addresses the usual technique bias by following the separation of data collection in time intervals (Podsakoff et al., 2012), beginning with data collection of independent variables, followed by data collection of mediators and dependent factors in the second interval. As a solution to the non-response bias, an advance cover letter was included in the mail that was addressed to the research population in order to obtain a high response rate (Donated, 1960; Luck, 1982). The cover letter informed respondents of the survey's duration and the aims of the investigation. The study analyzed early and late replies to determine their resemblance after collecting data over a six-week period. Armstrong and Overton introduced this technique for reducing similarity from responses (1977). In addition, the chi-square test revealed that the non-responsive bias had no effect on the results, as the demographic differences between the late and early respondents were not statistically significant (McHugh, 2013).

3.3 Research Instrument

The researcher collected data using a standardized questionnaire. The questionnaire is broken into two major sections, the first of which comprises preliminary demographic information and the second of which contains statements on the variables. To enhance participant comprehension, the variables have been arranged methodologically, i.e., the comments about the independent, mediator, and dependent variables have been grouped properly. In the present study, the researcher employed a five-point Likert scale, with values ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. The key argument for using this scale, as opposed to a 7-point or 9-point Likert scale, is that the respondent will better understand the option they select. It is also

recommended to use a 5-point scale when the number of observations is greater than 100. This study has almost 100 observations. Hence, a five-point scale is utilized (Leung, 2011). To ensure the validity and reliability of the research instrument, the measures or constructs for measuring the variables have been picked from prior research.

- **Acculturation:** The evaluation of acculturation was based on a ten-item scale. The scale was adapted from Stephenson's (2000) study and modified to meet the needs of the present investigation.
- The performance or poor website flow was evaluated based on the four items identified by Jiang, Adnan, Kaur, and Yang (2015). A sample item includes "The communication medium and website tools are efficient and helpful."
- The **online privacy** risk was evaluated based on the three items identified by Sweeney, Soutar, and Johnson (1999). A sample item includes "Online retailers may disclose my personal information (e.g. email address, mailing address) to other companies".

- **E-customer satisfaction:** Based on the three items defined by Udo, Bagchi, and Kirs (2010), e-customer satisfaction was evaluated.
- **Service orientation:** Based on the six items developed and updated by Alden, Steenkamp, and Batra (2006) and Westjohn, Arnold, Magnusson, and Reynolds, the foreigner service orientation was evaluated (2016).
- **Language barrier:** A five-item scale created by Downs and Hazen was utilized to assess the language barrier (1977).
- **Information seeking:** Based on the scale developed by Grace-Farfaglia, Dekkers, Sundararajan, Peters, and Park, information seeking was evaluated (2006). A typical statement is "The information I receive helps me to enhance my skills."
- **Purchase intention** was evaluated based on the three items identified in the study by Shin (2008). A sample item includes ". I recommend others to shop from online stores".

Results

Demographical characteristics

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Gender	N	%age
Male	244	55.1
Female	199	44.9
Age		
Less than 25-years	138	32.1
between the ages of 26 to 30	191	43.1
between the ages of 31 and 35	97	21.9
more than 35 years of age	17	3.8
Education		
Bachelor	217	49.2
Master	111	25.1
Higher	115	25.7

Table.1 the demographical characteristics of the sample were evaluated. The demographical information of the model shows that out of 443 total respondents, 244 were males, i.e. 55.1%, and 199 were female, i.e. 44.9%. The discrepancy in the gender distribution is merely due to the nature of the respondents that came forward to participate in the research study. The age statistics of the sample show

that 138 people were less than 25 years of age (31.2 %), 191 were between the ages of 26 to 30 (43.1%), 97 were between the ages of 31 and 35 (21.9 %), and 17 participants were more than 35 years of age (3.8 %). The age distribution shows that most foreigners were young and therefore possessed knowledge of online shopping. The sample's qualification or education statistics indicated that

most models had attained bachelor's and master's education (49.2 and 25.1%).

Descriptive Statistics

The data's descriptive statistics are computed to analyze the response pattern, normality and presence of extreme values in the data. The constructs' minimum and maximum values are evaluated to investigate the presence of outliers in the data. The

values are analogous to the ending points of the scale; thus, no outliers were originating in the statistics. The mean statistics of the constructs are above 3, thus showing that most of the sample agreed with the statements in the questionnaire. Lastly, Skewness point's values are evaluated for the data's normality. Skewness standards are contained by the threshold range of -1+1, thus appearing that the information is spread commonly (see table.2).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics Summarization

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Value	Value	Value	Value	Value	Std. Error
TInfoSeek	443	1.00	5.00	3.3557	1.08414	-.448	.116
LangBarir	443	1.00	9.80	3.3147	1.20453	.016	.116
PoorFoOri	443	1.00	5.00	3.4729	1.18691	-.379	.116
PoorWebF	443	1.00	5.00	3.3482	1.21137	-.361	.116
OnPrivRisk	443	1.00	5.00	3.1219	1.12438	-.137	.116
Acculturat	443	1.00	5.00	3.3193	1.17508	-.327	.116
ECustSat	443	1.00	5.00	3.4226	1.13984	-.288	.116
OnlinePInt	443	1.00	5.00	3.1847	1.16740	-.192	.116
List of avlid N	443						

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Factor Analysis through Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test checks for sample adequacy and measures for the data suitability. The threshold value of 0.8 must be crossed, and the results show that KMO statistics is 0.923 for this data which shows the

data sample to be adequate. The second test, Bartlett's test for Sphericity, checks for the occurrence of redundancy between variables and since the results show the significant value to be below 0.05, there is no redundancy in the data

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Sampling Adequacy of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure	.949
Sphericity Bartlett's Test	Chi-Square(Approx. value) 20855.944
	Df 741
	Sig. .000

4.4 Factors Results Analysis

Table 4 presents the results of the rotated component matrix, a crucial element within Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). This table serves as an instrument for examining both data accuracy and validity. The findings illustrate that

each component exhibits factor loadings exceeding 0.6, signifying the precision of these factor loadings. Furthermore, there is an absence of cross-loading concerns pertaining to any variables under investigation in this study.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix

	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PI1	.794							
PI2	.846							
PI3	.825							

IS1	.856				
IS2	.805				
IS3	.790				
IS4	.817				
IS5	.782				
LB1		.800			
LB2		.801			
LB3		.797			
LB4		.800			
LB5		.647			
FO1			.714		
FO2			.714		
FO3			.746		
FO4			.885		
FO5			.871		
FO6			.852		
WF1				.845	
WF2				.843	
WF3				.854	
WF4				.841	
PR1					.642
PR2					.713
PR3					.671
AC1					.806
AC2					.776
AC3					.806
AC4					.820
AC5					.793
AC6					.809
AC7					.872
AC8					.878
AC9					.888
AC10					.878
CS1					.645
CS2					.689
CS3					.666

4.5 Convergent and Discriminant Validation Assessment

Table 5 presents the results of convergent and discriminant validity tests conducted on the dataset. Convergent validity is demonstrated through the use of composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) indicators, which must be below the established threshold values of 0.7 and 0.5, respectively. The table exhibits that all variables

adhere to these threshold values, thereby indicating convergent validity. Furthermore, discriminant validity is evidenced by a diagonal formation in the table, illustrating that each variable exhibits a stronger association with itself as their respective values surpass those preceding them in sequence. Consequently, these findings substantiate the presence of both discriminant and convergent validity within the data utilized for this study.

Table 5: Convergent-Discriminant Validation Assessment Matrix

	CR	AVE	MSV	PR	PI	IS	FO	WF	AC	CS	LB
PR	0.872	0.695	0.468	0.834							
PI	0.917	0.786	0.415	0.644	0.887						
IS	0.910	0.668	0.171	0.362	0.413	0.818					
FO	0.945	0.742	0.479	0.229	0.196	0.375	0.861				
WF	0.905	0.807	0.468	0.684	0.585	0.404	0.252	0.952			
AC	0.911	0.772	0.368	0.572	0.461	0.400	0.417	0.557	0.879		
CS	0.954	0.872	0.406	0.590	0.402	0.403	0.637	0.506	0.607	0.934	
LB	0.924	0.713	0.479	0.239	0.314	0.363	0.692	0.242	0.428	0.567	0.844

4.6. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Table 6 presents the findings of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) conducted to assess the adequacy and fitness of the proposed model. The table comprises various fit indices, including Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and Chi-square/degrees of freedom ratio (CMIN).

each index. A thorough examination of Table 6 reveals that all calculated fit indices fall within their respective acceptable boundaries as specified by designated thresholds. Consequently, these results substantiate the overall fitness and viability of the proposed model in representing underlying data patterns effectively. This confirmation bolsters confidence in employing this model for subsequent analyses and interpretation.

Table 6: Model fitting performance indicators

CFA Indicators	CMIN/DF	GFI	IFI	CFI	RMSEA
Threshold points	≤ 3.0	≥ 0.81	≥ 0.91	≥ 0.91	≤ 0.080
Observed points	2.871	0.813	0.940	0.940	0.065

Figure 2: CFA

4.7. Structural Equation Model (SEM)

The obtained results of SEM on prescribed data are summarized in Table 7. It can be seen that troubled information-seeking significantly impacts online purchase intention. The influences of language barriers, online privacy risks, and acculturation exhibit substantial and positive effects on the respondents' online purchasing intentions. Consequently, the hypotheses positing direct relationships between these factors are corroborated.

In contrast, the impact of poor foreigner orientation and suboptimal website flow is deemed inconsequential; hence, their corresponding hypotheses are refuted.

Regarding E-customer satisfaction's mediating role, it demonstrates greater significance for all other independent variables compared to its relationship with poor website flow. As a result, the five remaining mediation hypotheses receive validation as well.

Table 7: SEM Results

Total Effect	TInfoSeek	LangBarir	PoorFoOri	PoorWebF	OnPrivRisk	Acculturat	ECustSat
ECustSat	.152**	.211**	.326**	.020	.124**	.179**	.000
OnlinePInt	.141**	.180**	-.123	.118	.260**	.216**	.333**
Direct Effect	TInfoSeek	LangBarir	PoorFoOri	PoorWebF	OnPrivRisk	Acculturat	ECustSat
ECustSat	.152**	.211**	.326**	.020	.124**	.179**	.000
OnlinePInt	.090*	.109**	-.231	.112	.219**	.156**	.333**
Indirect Effect	TInfoSeek	LangBarir	PoorFoOri	PoorWebF	OnPrivRisk	Acculturat	ECustSat
ECustSat	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
OnlinePInt	.051*	.070**	.109**	.007	.041*	.060**	.000

Figure 3: SEM

Eliberation and Conclusion

The online purchase intention of a customer is affected by several factors, privacy risk, layout and usefulness of the communication medium etc.

however, the situation becomes complicated when the purchase intention of migrants or foreigners is being evaluated in connection to the buying across the borders. In correspondence to the findings of

our study, Chen and Yao (2018) adopt an S-O-R (Stimulus-Organism-Response) centered framework has been employed to evaluate the influence of context-dependent variables on impulsive purchasing behaviors, specifically pertaining to the utilization of digital commerce experiences within the Chinese market. The empirical results revealed significant association the stimulating factors. i.e. language barrier, acculturation, online privacy risk, troubled information seeking and online purchase intention. Linking to the study findings, the scholarly work of Ariffin et al. (2018), Kizgin et al. (2018) and Pratama et al. (2017) recognize and discuss the impact of perceived risk, acculturation, information-seeking ability, language barriers and social commerce on the purchase intentions of consumers. This explains the buying paths which induce the foreigners to move online in routine consumption by developing a complete package of consideration by taking into account uncertainty, obstruct product or service information and the environment and believes. Previously, social studies showcased positive associations between service orientation and the comfort of foreign consumers. In a similar study, Bashir et al. (2019) evaluated the buying behaviors towards halal food items of South African consumers. The consumer's awareness regarding availability of halal nutriment products stocking by the department stores showed a foreign orientation, which led towards purchasing the food items. Other factors affect the consumption intentions of public, especially when the mode of shopping is shifted to online stores. Furthermore, the findings indicated indicate no relationship between poor foreigner orientation, poor website flow and online purchase intention. Reasoning that foreigners obtained helping patters which assist them to better access by using Chinese friends circle, classmate or other source to move toward online buying.

Conclusion

The present study's main objective was to evaluate foreigners' perceptions regarding online shopping patterns in China. For this purpose, the researcher collected data from foreigners living in China. The parameters of acculturation, online risk privacy, poor website flow, poor foreigner orientation, language barrier, troubling information seeking, e-customer

satisfaction and online purchase intention. Core findings of this research study are summarized as follows;

- The influence of heightened information-seeking behavior exhibits a constructive and significant effect on online buying intentions, demonstrating that as an individual's tendency to seek information intensifies, so too does their propensity to engage in online shopping.
- The impact of the language barrier is positive and significant on online purchase intention, showing that individuals are more inclined to divert towards online shopping if there is a language barrier.
- The impact of poor foreigner orientation is insignificant the inclination towards e-commerce transactions. The relationship shows that if these organizations do not consider the needs and requirements of foreign customers, there will be no change in the online purchase intention of the people.
- The relationship between poor website flow and online purchase intention is insignificant, showing that if the website isn't appropriately maintained, there will be no effect on the online purchase intention of customers.
- The cultural differences between local citizens and foreign nationals amplify international communities' proclivity for participating in e-commerce activities. This outcome highlights acculturation's weighty impact on bolstering web-based transactions among diverse populations.
- The mediation of E-customer satisfaction is significant for five associations. The findings show that the relationship between acculturation, troubling information seeking, online privacy risk, language barrier and poor foreigner orientation and online purchase intention is explained by E-customer satisfaction. However, the mediation of ECS on poor website flow is insignificant.

Implications, Limitations and Recommendations

The predominant constraint of the current study lies in its exclusive focus on data obtained from the clientele, specifically, international individuals engaged in e-commerce transactions. By broadening the scope of inquiry and incorporating diverse perspectives, this study could potentially yield more comprehensive and compelling findings. To enrich

the findings, future researchers should compare the findings from the nationals and foreigners to evaluate the differences in online purchasing patterns. Secondly the study is that the sample size is considerably small and doesn't reflect a country-wide generalization. Moreover, the data has only been collected from China. The study, including responses from similar countries like Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand etc., could offer a continental context of the confusion or misperceptions of people regarding use of E-commerce shopping intentions. Thirdly the study is that the tests and approaches employed in this research are minimal and only analyze the data from an objective perspective. Keeping these limitations in view, there is a scope for future researchers to distinguish and enrich the study design by adopting a subjectivist and objective approach.

This study concerns online shopping among foreigners in china online shopping by replacing traditional shopping, thus providing an easy way for foreigners too in marketing their products to other online shoppers. Different factors, such as website locking during payment, privacy risks written in Chinese language, product description in Chinese and cultural information about the Chinese especially mentioned on purchase items, lead to poor impact for buying by foreigners. This study helps overcome the barriers to online purchasing instated on non-online shopping. The findings in our study are significantly helpful for shopping online vendor's also foreign visitors. The stress on the China is an educational and business hub; thus, the number of foreigners is increasing each year, and an improvement in the foreigner orientation will increase the profitability of the organizations. The present study makes significant theoretical contributions by posing SOR-based research and online shopping behaviour. The study contributed to the body of knowledge regarding the human satisfaction by the means of consumption habits. This research work contains knowledge of marketing domain and explored empirically. Moreover, the present study's findings are essential for foreigners in China because it gives them opportunities to forecast and understand the measures in online shopping. It also allows them to evaluate the effectiveness of

online privacy and website flow regarding online shopping in China.

REFERENCES

1. Agten, S. (2021). The Chinese Online Tsunami. In *Adventures in the Chinese Economy: 16 Years from the Inside* (pp. 115-136): Springer.
2. A literature review. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 15(1), 102-121. Mutum, D., & Ghazali, E. (2006). Online shoppers vs non-shoppers: a lifestyle study of Malaysian internet users. In *International Proceedings of AGBA 3rd World Congress* (Vol. 3, pp. 4-6).
3. Ahmad, W., Attiq, S., Ahmad, A., Ilyas, A., & Kulsoom, K. (2019). Investigating the impact of Consumer's Involvement, Risk-taking Personality, Internet Self-Efficacy, Life Style and Privacy Concern on Online Purchase Intention and Shopping Adoption. *Pakistan Business Review*, 20(3), 582-599.
4. Ajay Kaushik, N., & Potti Srinivasa, R. (2017). Effect of Website Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Purchase Intention in Online Travel Ticket Booking Websites. *Management*, 7(5), 168-173.
5. Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
6. Alden, D. L., Steenkamp, J.-B. E., & Batra, R. (2006). Consumer attitudes toward marketplace globalization: Structure, antecedents and consequences. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 23(3), 227-239.
7. Ani, N., Noprisson, H., & Ali, N. M. (2019). Measuring usability and purchase intention for online travel booking: A case study. *International Review of Applied Sciences and Engineering*, 10(2), 165-171.
8. Ariffin, S. K., Mohan, T., & Goh, Y.-N. (2018). Influence of consumers' perceived risk on consumers' online purchase intention. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*.

9. Armstrong, J. S., & Overton, T. S. (1977). Estimating nonresponse bias in mail surveys. *Journal of marketing research*, 14(3), 396-402.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/002224377701400320>
10. Bashir, A. M., Bayat, A., Olutuase, S. O., & Abdul Latiff, Z. A. (2019). Factors affecting consumers' intention towards purchasing halal food in South Africa: a structural equation modelling. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 25(1), 26-48.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/10454446.2018.1452813>
11. Beck, L., & Ajzen, I. (1991). Predicting dishonest actions using the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of research in personality*, 25(3), 285-301.
12. Bhatti, A., & Rehman, S. U. (2020). Perceived benefits and perceived risks effect on online shopping behavior with the mediating role of consumer purchase intention in Pakistan. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 26(1), 33-54.
13. Bhatti, A., Saad, S., & Gbadebo, S. M. (2018). Convenience risk, product risk, and perceived risk influence on online shopping: Moderating effect of attitude. *Science Arena Publications International journal of Business Management*, 3(2), 1-11.
14. Brüseke, L. (2016). The influence of privacy perceptions on online shopping behavior: a comparison between millennials and baby boomers. University of Twente,
15. Buxbaum, O. (2016). The SOR-Model. In *Key Insights into Basic Mechanisms of Mental Activity* (pp. 7-9): Springer.
16. Chaudary, S., Rehman, M. A., & Nisar, S. (2014). Factors influencing the acceptance of online shopping in Pakistan.
17. Chen, C.-C., & Yao, J.-Y. (2018). What drives impulse buying behaviors in a mobile auction? The perspective of the Stimulus-Organism-Response model. *Telematics Informatics*, 35(5), 1249-1262.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2018.02.007>
18. Cheng, J.-C., Chen, C.-Y., Yen, C.-H., & Teng, H.-Y. (2017). Building customer satisfaction with tour leaders: The roles of customer trust, justice perception, and cooperation in group package tours. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 22(4), 395-407.
19. Chi, T. (2018). Mobile commerce website success: Antecedents of consumer satisfaction and purchase intention. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, 17(3), 189-215.
20. Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P., & Warshaw, P. R. (1989). User acceptance of computer technology: a comparison of two theoretical models. *Management science*, 35(8), 982-1003.
21. Dai, H., & Palvi, P. C. (2009). Mobile commerce adoption in China and the United States: a cross-cultural study. *ACM SIGMIS Database: the DATABASE for Advances in Information Systems*, 40(4), 43-61.
22. Dey, B. L., Yen, D., & Samuel, L. (2020). Digital consumer culture and digital acculturation. *International Journal of Information Management*, 51, 102057.
23. Downs, C. W., & Hazen, M. D. (1977). A factor analytic study of communication satisfaction. *The Journal of Business Communication*, 14(3), 63-73.
24. Dwivedi, Y. K., Hughes, D. L., Coombs, C., Constantiou, I., Duan, Y., Edwards, J. S., . . . Prashant, P. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on information management research and practice: Transforming education, work and life. *International Journal of Information Management*, 55, 102211.
25. Eloat, K., Huang, A., & Lehnich, M. (2013). A new era for manufacturing in China. *McKinsey Quarterly*, 1(6), 1-14.
26. Gill, B., & Huang, Y. (2006). Sources and limits of Chinese 'soft power'. *Survival*, 48(2), 17-36.
27. Goldstein, A. (2001). The diplomatic face of China's grand strategy: a rising power's emerging choice. *The China Quarterly*, 168, 835-864.

28. Grace-Farfaglia, P., Dekkers, A., Sundararajan, B., Peters, L., & Park, S.-H. (2006). Multinational web uses and gratifications: Measuring the social impact of online community participation across national boundaries. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 6(1), 75-101.
29. Granello, D. H., & Wheaton, J. E. (2004). Online data collection: Strategies for research. *Journal of Counseling Development*, 82(4), 387-393. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1556-6678.2004.tb00325.x>
30. Guan, M., Cha, M., Li, Y., Wang, Y., & Sun, J. (2020). From Anticipation to Action: Data Reveal Mobile Shopping Patterns During a Yearly Mega Sale Event in China. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*.
31. Hao, Y., & Choi, S. U. (2019). Operating Performance of Chinese Online Shopping Companies: An Analysis Using DuPont Components. *Sustainability*, 11(13), 3602.
32. Hidayatullah, S., PPS, L. P., Prasetya, D. A., Rakhmadani, D. P., Rachmawati, I. K., & Windhyastiti, I. (2020). Website Quality: The Effect with Perceived Flow and Purchase Intention in Travel Customers in Malang City.
33. Jackson, S. L., & Dear, D. (2016). Resource extraction and national anxieties: China's economic presence in Mongolia. *Eurasian Geography and Economics*, 57(3), 343-373.
34. Jamal, A., Kizgin, H., Rana, N. P., Laroche, M., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2019). Impact of acculturation, online participation and involvement on voting intentions. *Government Information Quarterly*, 36(3), 510-519.
35. Jeon, M. M., & Jeong, M. (2017). Customers' perceived website service quality and its effects on e-loyalty. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*.
36. Jiang, N., Adnan, M. M. B. M., Kaur, M. K. M., & Yang, X. Y. J. I. J. o. B. (2015). The Effect of Website Performance and Online Retailer Status on Consumer Purchase Intention: A Mediator Role of Buyer Perception. *International Journal of Business Management Accounting Research*, 10(10), 158.
37. Kaya, B., Behraves, E., Abubakar, A. M., Kaya, O. S., & Orús, C. (2019). The moderating role of website familiarity in the relationships between e-service quality, e-satisfaction and e-loyalty. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, 18(4), 369-394.
38. Khatoon, S., Zhengliang, X., & Hussain, H. (2020). The Mediating Effect of Customer Satisfaction on the Relationship Between Electronic Banking Service Quality and Customer Purchase Intention: Evidence From the Qatar Banking Sector. *Sage open*, 10(2), 2158244020935887.
39. King, R. C., Schilhavy, R. A., Chowa, C., & Chin, W. W. (2016). Do customers identify with our website? The effects of website identification on repeat purchase intention. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 20(3), 319-354.
40. Kizgin, H., Dey, B. L., Dwivedi, Y. K., Hughes, L., Jamal, A., Jones, P., . . . Richard, M.-O. (2020). The impact of social media on consumer acculturation: Current challenges, opportunities, and an agenda for research and practice. *International Journal of Information Management*, 51, 102026.
41. Kizgin, H., Jamal, A., Dey, B. L., & Rana, N. P. (2018). The Impact of Social Media on Consumers' Acculturation and Purchase Intentions. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 20(3), 503-514. doi:10.1007/s10796-017-9817-4
42. Kumar, V., & Dange, U. (2014). A study on perceived risk in online shopping of youth in Pune: A factor analysis. *Acme Intellects International Journal of Research in Management, Social Sciences & Technology*, 8(8), 1-9

43. Leung, S.-O. (2011). A Comparison of Psychometric Properties and Normality in 4-, 5-, 6-, and 11-Point Likert Scales. *Journal of Social Service Research*, 37(4), 412-421. doi:10.1080/01488376.2011.580697
44. Leung, G. C. (2011). China's energy security: perception and reality. *Energy Policy*, 39(3), 1330-1337.
45. Lisichkova, N., & Othman, Z. (2017). The impact of influencers on online purchase intent. In.
46. Lissitsa, S., & Kol, O. (2019). Four generational cohorts and hedonic m-shopping: Association between personality traits and purchase intention. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 1-26.
47. Lim, Y. J., Osman, A., Salahuddin, S. N., Romle, A. R., & Abdullah, S. (2016). Factors influencing online shopping behavior: the mediating role of purchase intention. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 35(October 2015), 401-410
48. Ling, L. P., & Yazdanifard, R. (2014). Does gender play a role in online consumer behavior? *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: E Marketing*, 14(7), 1-9
49. Maharsi, A. R., Njotoprajitno, R. S., Hadianto, B., & Wiraatmaja, J. (2021). The Effect of Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction on Purchasing Intention: A Case Study in Indonesia. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(4), 475-482.
50. Maher, A. A., & Elsharnouby, T. H. (2020). Foreigner service orientation: does the perception of other consumers matter? *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 37(3), 305-315. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/JCM-11-2018-2931>
51. Makmor, N., Aziz Abd, N., & Alam Shah, S. (2019). Social Commerce an Extended Technology Acceptance Model: The Mediating Effect of Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness. *Malays. J. Consum. Fam. Econ*, 22, 119-136.
52. McHugh, M. L. (2013). The chi-square test of independence. *Biochemia medica: Biochemia medica*, 23(2), 143-149. doi:<https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2013.018>
53. Mittal, A. (2013). E-commerce: It 's Impact on consumer behavior. *Global Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 3(2), 131-138
54. Narayanan, M., Koo, B., & Cozzarin, B. P. (2012). Fear of fraud and Internet purchasing. *Applied Economics Letters*, 19(0), 1615-1619.
55. Nazir, S., Tayyab, A., Sajid, A., Ur Rashid, H., & Javed, I. (2012). How online shopping is affecting consumers buying behavior in Pakistan? *IJCSI International Journal of Computer Science*, 9(3), 486-495.
56. Nepomuceno, M. V., Laroche, M., & Richard, M. O. (2014). How to reduce perceived risk when buying online: The interactions between intangibility, product knowledge, brand familiarity, privacy and security concerns. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 21(4), 619-629.
57. Nuryakin, & Farida, N. (2016). Effects of convenience online shopping and satisfaction on repeatpurchase intention among students of higher institutions in Indonesia. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*, 21(2).
58. Opoku, A. (2016). The mediating role of customer satisfaction in the relationship between service quality and customer retention in the rural banks in Ashanti Region.
59. Pratama, M. O., Meiyanti, R., Noprisson, H., Ramadhan, A., & Hidayanto, A. N. (2017). Influencing factors of consumer purchase intention based on social commerce paradigm. Paper presented at the 2017 International Conference on Advanced Computer Science and Information Systems (ICACISIS).

60. Rahi, S., Ghani, M. A., & Ngah, A. H. (2020). Factors propelling the adoption of internet banking: the role of e-customer service, website design, brand image and customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Business Information Systems*, 33(4), 549-569.
61. Rita, P., Oliveira, T., & Farisa, A. (2019). The impact of e-service quality and customer satisfaction on customer behavior in online shopping. *Heliyon*, 5(10), e02690.
62. Shambaugh, D. (2015). China's soft-power push: The search for respect. *Foreign Affairs*, 94(4), 99-107.
63. Sheehan, K. B. (2001). Email Survey Response Rates: a Review. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 6(2). doi:10.1111/j.1083-6101.2001.tb00117.x
64. Shin, D. H. (2008). Understanding purchasing behaviors in a virtual economy: Consumer behavior involving virtual currency in Web 2.0 communities. *Interacting with computers*, 20(4-5), 433-446.
65. Shirk, S. L. (2007). Changing media, changing foreign policy in China. *Japanese Journal of Political Science*, 8(1), 43-70.
66. Singh, S., & Srivastava, S. (2018). Moderating effect of product type on online shopping behaviour and purchase intention: An Indian perspective. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 5(1), 1495043.
67. Stephenson, M. (2000). Development and validation of the Stephenson Multigroup Acculturation Scale (SMAS). *Psychological assessment*, 12(1), 77.
68. Sweeney, J. C., Soutar, G. N., & Johnson, L. W. (1999). The role of perceived risk in the quality-value relationship: A study in a retail environment. *Journal of retailing*, 75(1), 77-105. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359\(99\)80005-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359(99)80005-0).
69. Taghipour, A., Ahadi, N., Sornsaruht, P., Deebhijarn, S., dos Santos, N. M. R., Saengratwatchara, P., . . . Poopichayapongse, P. (2018). PRODUCT IMAGE INFLUENCE OF THAILAND JEWELRY ENTERPRISES ON EXPATRIATE'S PURCHASE INTENTION ON GOLD JEWELRY IN THAILAND. *International Journal of Industrial Management*, 5.
70. Udo, G. J., Bagchi, K. K., & Kirs, P. J. (2010). An assessment of customers'e-service quality perception, satisfaction and intention. *International Journal of Information Management*, 30(6), 481-492. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2010.03.005>
71. Vakulenko, Y., Shams, P., Hellström, D., & Hjort, K. (2019). Online retail experience and customer satisfaction: the mediating role of last mile delivery. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 29(3), 306-320.
72. Valaei, N., Rezaei, S., Ismail, W. K. W., & Oh, Y. M. (2016). The effect of culture on attitude towards online advertising and online brands: applying Hofstede's cultural factors to internet marketing. *International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising*, 10(4), 270-301.
73. Ventre, I., & Kolbe, D. (2020). The Impact of Perceived Usefulness of Online Reviews, Trust and Perceived Risk on Online Purchase Intention in Emerging Markets: A Mexican Perspective. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 1-13.
74. Vohra, A., & Bhardwaj, N. (2019). From active participation to engagement in online communities: Analysing the mediating role of trust and commitment. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 25(1), 89-114.
75. Wang, X., Yu, C., & Wei, Y. (2012). Social Media Peer Communication and Impacts on Purchase Intentions: A Consumer Socialization Framework. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 26(4), 198-208. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2011.11.004>

76. Westjohn, S. A., Arnold, M. J., Magnusson, P., & Reynolds, K. (2016). The influence of regulatory focus on global consumption orientation and preference for global versus local consumer culture positioning. *Journal of International Marketing*, 24(2), 22-39.
77. Weitz, R. (2010). Nervous neighbors: China finds a sphere of influence. *World Affs.*, 173, 6.
78. Wirani, Y., Diniputri, L., & Romadhon, M. S. (2020). Investigating the Influence of Information Quality, Information Seeking, and Familiarity with Purchase Intentions: A Perspective of Instagram Users in Indonesia. Paper presented at the 2020 8th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT).
79. Wirawati, S. M., Arthawati, S. N., Khamaludin, M. F., Novitasari, D., Adwiyah, R., & Juwaini, A. (2021). The Effect of Social Media, Consumer Trust and E-Service Quality on Purchase Intention of Online Transportation Services. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 7686-7695-7686-7695.
80. Yaobin, L., & Tao, Z. (2007). A research of consumers' initial trust in online stores in China. *Journal of research and practice in information technology*, 39(3), 167-180.
81. Zhao, S. (2013). Foreign policy implications of Chinese nationalism revisited: The strident turn. *Journal of Contemporary China*, 22(82), 535-553.
82. Zhang, L. E., Harzing, A.-W., & Fan, S. X. (2018). The Impact of Host Country Language Skills on Expatriate Adjustment and the Expatriate-Local Relationship. In *Managing Expatriates in China* (pp. 91-119): Springer.
83. Zhu, W., Mou, J., & Benyoucef, M. (2019). Exploring purchase intention in cross-border E-commerce: A three stage model. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 51, 320-330.
84. [84]Junqian Ma. (2020). Supporting Practices to Break Chinese International Students' Language Barriers:The First Step to Facilitate Their Social Adjustment. *Journal of International Students*, 10 (1), pp. 84-105
85. [85] Boban Melovi'c, Damir Sehovi'c, Vesna Karad'zi'c, Marina Dabi'c, Dragana Cirovi'c. (2021). Determinants of Millennials' behavior in online shopping – Implications on consumers' satisfaction and e-business development. *Technology in Society*, 65. 101561.
86. [86]Chen, Y., Yan, X., Fan, W. and Gordon, M. (2015) 'The joint moderating role of trust propensity and gender on consumers' online shopping behavior', *Computers in Human Behavior*, 28 February, Vol. 43, pp.272-283.
87. [87]Bhatnagar, A. and Ghose, S. (2004) 'A latent class segmentation analysis of e-shoppers', *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 57, No. 7, pp.758-767.
88. [88]Liao, Z. and Cheung, M.T. (2001) 'Internet-based e-shopping and consumer attitudes: an empirical study', *Information & Management*, Vol. 38, No. 5, pp.299-306.
89. [89]Eroglu, S.A., Machleit, K.A. and Davis, L.M. (2003) 'Empirical testing of a model of online store atmospherics and shopper responses', *Psychology & Marketing*, Vol. 20, No. 2, pp.139-150
90. [90]Islam, Md, S. (2021). Online Shopping Behavior among International Students from Belt & Road Countries in China. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6 (1), 63-75.
91. [91]Cheng, H. and Fu, T. (2018). The Determinants of Online Shopping Behavior. [online] IEEE Xplore. Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8494098> [Accessed 24 Nov. 2020].
92. [92]Clemes, M.D., Gan, C. and Zhang, J. (2014). An empirical analysis of online shopping adoption in Beijing, China *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, online]21(3),pp.364-375.Available at: https://ideas.repec.org/a/eee/joreco/v21y2_014i3p364-375.html [Accessed 23 Nov. 2020].

93. [93]Junqian Ma. (2020). Supporting Practices to Break Chinese International Students' Language Barriers: The First Step to Facilitate Their Social Adjustment. *Journal of International Students*, 10 (1), pp. 84- 105
94. [94]Rashed, M. S & Ashraf Un, N. (2016). Doing Business in and with China: The Challenges are Great, but so are the Opportunities, *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: B Economics and Commerce*, 16 (2), 1-9.
95. [95]Spradley, J. P. (1979). *The ethnographic interview*. New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston. Cresswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2011). *Designing and Conducting mixed method research* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
96. [96]Bernard, H. R. (2002). *Research methods in anthropology: Qualitative and quantitative approaches* (3rd ed.). Walnut Creek, CA: Alta Mira Press.
97. [97]Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American journal of theoretical and applied statistics*, 5(1), 1-4.
98. [98]Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., and Podsakoff, N. P. (2012). Sources of method bias in social science research and recommendations on how to control it. *Annual Review of Psychology*. 63, 539- 569. doi: 10.1146/annurev-psych-120710-100452.
99. [99]Donald, M. N. (1960). Implications of Nonresponse for the interpretation of Mail Questionnaire Data. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 24.P-99-114.
100. [100]Luck, D.J. (1982). Hugh, G., Wales., Donald, A., Taylor & Rubin, R.S. (1982). *Marketing Research*, (6th ed), Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc., pp, 276-279.
101. Zulfikar Ali received the bachelor's degree in Commerce from Karachi University in 2010, the master's degree in Economics and Finance from Karakorum International University in 2013 and the philosophy of doctorate degree in information behavior from Kunming university of science and technology in 2022, respectively. His research areas include mobile payments and knowledge management.

